

Artificial Intelligence Technologies Required in Business Education in South-South Universities

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Abstract

This study assessed Application of Artificial Intelligence technologies required in business education in South-South Universities in Nigeria. Two research questions and Four (4) hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted descriptive survey design, the targeted population comprises 236; The breakdown is 135 business education lecturers in state universities and 101 business education lecturers in federal universities. The population served as sample. A 27-item questionnaire was the instrument used for data collection. The questionnaire was structured on a 4-point scale: Very High Extent (VHE) – 4 points, High Extent (HE) – 3 points, Low Extent (LE) – 2 points, Very Low Extent (VLE) – 1 point. There was face and content validity of the questionnaire. The questionnaire was given to two experts in computer science, three experts in measurement and evaluation and two experts in business education at the Delta State University, Abraka. In order to ensure the internal consistency of the instrument, a total of 13 copies of the questionnaire were administered to 13 lecturers in business education at Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka in South East, Nigeria which is not part of the study. The data obtained were subjected to Cronbach Alpha which yielded the reliability co-efficient of 0.86 and 0.84 on research question 1 and 2 respectively. A total of 243 copies of the questionnaire were administered to 243 lecturers and 236 were fully completed and returned within a period of two weeks. There was return rate of 97.11%. The data collected were analyzed using mean and standard deviations. T-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. If t-calculated value is less than t-critical, hypothesis is accepted. If the t-calculated value is greater than t-critical, hypotheses is rejected. The findings of research question one are AI-powered educational games, Adaptive learning platforms, among others. The findings of research question two are AI supports the presentation of lectures in business education, AI assists lecturers to carry out research in business education among others. The findings on the hypotheses are There is no significant difference in the mean rating between male and female on extent of Artificial Intelligence technologies required in business education in South-South Universities in Nigeria, there is no significant difference in the mean rating between male and female on the extent of influence of Artificial Intelligence technologies required in business education in South-South Universities in Nigeria among others.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Technologies, Business Education, South-South Universities.

Introduction

Business educators have the responsibility of classroom instructional delivery to business education students in a tertiary institution. Deployment of AI in tertiary institutions can aid effective delivery of instruction in business education. The business educator is one who is well-trained and well groomed in principle and in practice in the broad field of Business Education. Business Education is a

programme of instruction which consists of two parts (a) Office Education: being a vocational education for office careers through initial, refresher and upgrading education leading to employability and advancement in office occupation and (b) general business: being a programme of instruction to provide students with information and competencies which are needed by all in managing personal business affairs and in using the services of the business world. Business educators hold the key to all instructions in Business Education or Business Studies. Both in tertiary institutions and in secondary schools. business educators are saddled with the responsibilities of instructional planning and delivering to the students. AI has many facilities aiding the effective presentation of lectures in tertiary institutions. Bordia (2023) opines that lecturers in tertiary institutions can use AI-powered chatbots to provide uninterrupted learning to students. As chatbots are available, students can use them to resolve doubts in real time. Moreover, chatbots can also be used by school authorities to provide information to parents and students. For example, details on fees, new admissions, classes, etc., can be passed on to parents and students through AI-powered chatbots. Tasks such as grading assignments, generating reports, and managing administrative paperwork can be automated, leading to increased efficiency and improved teacher-student interactions (Chen et al., 2020; Borbajo et al., 2023). AI integration empowers teachers to use AI as a tool to enhance instruction (Singh & Jain 2022; Ogunode, Agbade & Bassey 2023b). The teaching programme covers the preparation of lecture notes, presentation of lectures, assessment of students' academic programmes via tests and examinations, marking of students' scripts, preparation of students' integration of resources into lecture presentations and classroom management. These things that constitute teaching programmes can be easily done by the deployment of Artificial Intelligence by Business educators who teach business education.

Business educators are also responsible for setting exam questions for their respective courses during the semesters, while tertiary institutions' management handles examinations. Deployment of AI in tertiary institutions can aid effective learning engagement and collaboration among learners. Westagilelabs (2022) asserts that voice assistants are engaging and convenient ways to bring learning at home while also helping users schedule study calendars, listen to coaching instructions while on the go, and give instant answers to students' basic questions in class. The benefits of voice assistants in education include: efficient saving of time for students and teachers, providing community learning opportunities, and providing personalized education within seconds. AI technologies have proven to be useful in assisting lecturers to set examination questions and also aid institutions to conduct effective examinations. AI can help grade exams using an answer key; it can also "compile data about how students performed and even grade more abstract assessments such as essays. Ogunode and Gregory (2023) assert that AI can assist teachers and lecturers, especially exam officers, prepare students results very fast and reliable. Also, Ogunode, Edinoh & Chinedu (2023) submit that AI can help conduct fair exams with the use of AI-powered remote proctoring. With its help, school authorities can easily conduct exams for remote learners. The authorities can prevent cheating during exams by analyzing the images/video streams produced by AI proctors. These proctors keep an eye on the candidate by detecting voices or presence of another person from the examinee. Lecturers can also use AI to manage their course materials. Bordia (2023) asserts that one of the ways this technology can be used is to improve the quality of courses offered online and offline. Research has shown that the dropout rates in online courses are relatively high. Also, the dropout rate in schools is on the higher side. It can happen due to multiple reasons like lack of clarity in understanding different concepts or the inability of teachers to identify the gaps in learning materials/lecturers. AI can fill these gaps by analyzing how students interact with different course materials. Using this data, the course quality can be improved.

Effective and efficient implementation of business education programme in Nigerian tertiary institutions requires both human and material resources such as ICT and the application of Artificial Intelligence. Artificial Intelligence (AI) is finding relevance as one of the emerging technologies which bring about effectiveness in the teaching and learning process. In the advanced countries of the world,

AI has been integrated into the educational sector, especially in the tertiary institutions, to aid implementation of the curriculum. Ogunode, Agbade & Bassey (2023) view AI as programs designed with human-like intelligence and structured in forms of computers, robot, or other machines to aid in the provision of any kind of service or tasks to improve social, economic and political development of the society. Frankenfield (2023) defines Artificial Intelligence (AI) as a simulation of human intelligence by software-coded heuristics. Artificial intelligence is a branch of business that produces and studies the machines aimed at the stimulation of human intelligence processes. For Copeland (2023), Artificial Intelligence (AI) can be defined as the ability of a digital computer or computer controlled robot to perform tasks commonly associated with intelligent beings. The term is frequently applied to the project of developing systems endowed with the intellectual processes characteristic of humans, such as the ability to reason and discover meaning. Its machine programme forms have capacities and abilities to execute tasks and responsibilities that human beings perform with the assistance of human-like intelligence.

AI has aided many tertiary institutions to move from the traditional method of teaching to online platforms. Westagilelabs (2022) maintains that using VR technologies, students can directly connect to their mobile devices or laptops and access content interactively. Virtual learning environments can offer group educational experiences, provide student counselling services, and facilitate an immersive learning experience. VR headsets can help students with ADD/ADHD by blocking out distractions and increasing attention spans. Additionally, they can also aid learners in soft skill coaching, life skills, and self-development with interactive virtual simulations. Also, Bordia (2023) asserts that with the help of AI, students can learn from anywhere at their own pace without having to attend physical classes. They can connect with learners from all over the world and participate in similar course. AI is modifying education models and teaching/learning techniques around the globe. As learners can quickly access information, they can resolve their doubts in a short time. This powerful technology is also promoting the culture of lifelong learning by empowering students with the required information in a span of a few seconds. Deployment of AI in tertiary institutions can assist lecturers to use a variety of teaching methods to teach science education in the tertiary institutions. Borbajo et al (2023a) ascertain that AI integration in the classroom offer support for diverse learning styles and individual needs. Through the use of natural language processing and machine learning algorithms, AI tools could accommodate various learning preferences, such as visual, auditory, or kinesthetic. Students with learning difficulties or special needs also benefit from AI-powered assistive technologies, which provide tailored interventions and accommodations, enabling them to access and engage with the curriculum more effectively. Ogunode, Edinoh and Chinedu (2023) opine that AI systems can “gauge a student’s learning style and pre-existing knowledge to deliver customized support and instruction.

Empirical Studies

At study titled Artificial Intelligence as modern technologies for teaching and learning of business education in tertiary institutions was carried out by Eze, Igwe and Okah (2023). Descriptive survey research design was adopted. The population of the study was four hundred and twenty-five business educators in North Central Nigeria. Due to the small size of the population, the entire population was studied; therefore, there was no sampling. The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire. Data for the study were collected with the help of four research assistants. Data collected were analyzed using mean and standard deviations to answer the research questions, while t-test was used to test the hypotheses. The study found that Intelligent Tutoring System (ITS), Expert System (ES), Machine-assisted classroom, Deep Learning (DL), Voice assistants’ technologies, Robotics, Machine Vision (MV) and Automated Facial Recognition (FR) are Artificial Intelligence tools for teaching and learning of business education. The study also found that AI supports lecturers in research activities by automating data analysis and expediting the research process. Thereby aiding decision-making and

generating valuable insights. In conclusion, the paper shows that the impact of AI on the teaching and research experience of university lecturers is substantial. The integration of AI technologies offers benefits such as enhanced personalized learning.

Olom, Kulo & Atah (2025) carried out a study titled Adoption and Utilization of Artificial Intelligence Tools in Marketing Consumer Goods in Nigeria which examined the adoption and utilization of Artificial Intelligence tools in marketing consumer goods in Nigeria. The study adopted a descriptive survey design. The population comprised 516 registered enterprises in Cross River State. The instrument for data collection was a researcher's self-designed questionnaire titled Adoption and Utilization of Artificial Intelligence Tools in Marketing Consumer Goods Rating Scale (AUAIMCGRS). The instrument was validated by two experts in the department of Business Education at the University of Calabar and tested for reliability using the Cronbach Alpha coefficient, which yielded a coefficient of 0.87. Data were analyzed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions, and an independent t-test was used to test the research hypotheses. The findings of the study indicate that the adoption and utilization of content creation and curation tools and automated email marketing tools enhance the marketing of consumer goods in Nigeria. It was recommended, among other things, that the brands should continue to adopt AI-driven content creation and automated email marketing tools to streamline and enhance their marketing efforts.

Statement of the Problem

The goals of education in Nigeria comprise the development of appropriate skills, mental, physical and social abilities and competencies to empower individuals to live in and contribute positively to the society. Therefore, the teaching-learning process ought to make the most of the potentials and abilities of the individual for self-fulfillment for a successful learning experience. This would imply that individual learners should be able to make constructive and well guided learning strategies towards the attainment of their individual goals especially academic success. The integration of Artificial Intelligence tools will help to a great extent to facilitate teaching and learning in the educational system, most especially in business education. The utilization of AI tools in business education is low. The statement of the problem therefore is to what extent are Artificial Intelligence technologies required in business education in South-South Universities?

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of the study is to assess Artificial Intelligence technologies required in business education in South-South Universities. Specifically, the objectives are:

1. To determine the extent of Artificial Intelligence technologies required in business education in South-South Universities in Nigeria.
2. To determine the extent of the influence of Artificial Intelligence technologies required in business education in South-South Universities in Nigeria.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What is the extent of Artificial Intelligence technologies required in business education in South-South Universities in Nigeria?
2. What is the extent of the influence of Artificial Intelligence technologies required in business education in South-South Universities in Nigeria?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses are tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference in the mean rating between male and female on extent of artificial Intelligence technologies required in business education in South-South Universities in Nigeria.
2. There is no significant difference in the mean rating between male and female on extent of the influence of Artificial Intelligence technologies required in business education in South-South Universities in Nigeria.
3. There is no significant difference in the mean rating between state and federal university lecturers on extent of Artificial Intelligence technologies required in business education in South-South Universities in Nigeria.
4. There is no significant difference in the mean rating between state and federal university lecturers on extent of influence of Artificial Intelligence technologies required in business education in South-South Universities in Nigeria.

Method

The study adopted descriptive survey design. The descriptive survey is suitable because there is no manipulation of data (Okoro, 2024). The study was guided with 2 research questions and 4 hypotheses. The targeted population comprises 236. The breakdown is 135 business education lecturers in state universities and 101 business education lecturers in federal universities. The entire population was used for the study, since the population was manageable. There was no sampling.

A 26-item questionnaire was the instrument used for data collection. The questionnaire was divided into two parts: Part A contained five (5) items of demographic variables of the respondents – Name of university, Type of university, Rank, Sex, Job experience. Part B contained 21 items based on the two (2) research questions. Research question one (1): What is the extent of Artificial Intelligence technologies required in business education in South-South Universities in Nigeria? contained 10 items. Research question two (2): What is the extent of the influence of Artificial Intelligence technologies required in business education in South-South Universities in Nigeria? contained 11 items. The questionnaire was structured on a 4-point scale of responses: Very High Extent (VHE), High Extent (HE), Low Extent (LE), Very Low Extent (VLE). There was face and content validity of the questionnaire. The questionnaire was given to two experts in computer science, three experts in measurement and evaluation and two experts in business education at the Delta State University, Abraka. The experts made necessary corrections and suggestions which were effected before the final copy was written. In order to ensure the internal consistency of the instrument, a total of 13 copies of the questionnaire were administered to 13 lecturers in business education at Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka in South East, Nigeria which is not part of the study. The data obtained were subjected to Cronbach Alpha which yielded the reliability coefficient of 0.86 and 0.84 on research question 1 and 2 respectively. A total of 243 copies of the questionnaire were administered to 243 lecturers and 236 copies were fully completed and returned within a period of two weeks. There was return rate of 97.11%. The data collected were weighted and analyzed as follows: Very High Extent (VHE) – 4 points, High Extent (HE) – 3 points, Low Extent (LE) – 2 points, Very Low Extent (VLE) - 1 point. Any item with a mean score of 2.5 and above is regarded as High Extent while any item below 2.5 is regarded as Low Extent. T-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. If t-calculated value is less than t-critical, hypothesis is accepted, while if the t-calculated value is greater than t-critical, hypotheses is rejected.

RESULT

Research Question 1: What is the extent of Artificial Intelligence technologies required in business education in South-South Universities in Nigeria?

Table 1: Mean responses of male and female on extent of Artificial Intelligence technologies required in business education in South-South Universities in Nigeria. N = 236.

S/N	Extent of Artificial Intelligence technologies required in business education:	\bar{x}	Std. Dev	Decision
1	AI-powered educational games	3.10	0.82	HE
2	Adaptive learning platforms	2.98	0.85	HE
3	Intelligent Tutoring System (ITS)	3.19	0.84	HE
4	Expert System (ES)	3.11	0.91	HE
5	Machine-assisted classroom	3.06	0.88	HE
6	Deep-Learning (DL)	2.93	0.78	HE
7	Voice assistant technologies	2.86	0.77	HE
8	Robotics	2.99	0.83	HE
9	Machine Vision (MV)	3.01	0.92	HE
10	Automated Facial Recognition (FR)	3.12	0.85	HE
Aggregate Mean				
Criterion Mean				

Research Question 2: What is the extent of the influences of Artificial Intelligence technologies required in business education in South-South Universities in Nigeria?

Table 2: Mean responses of male and female on extent of the influence of Artificial Intelligence technologies required in business education in South-South Universities in Nigeria. N = 236.

S/N	Extent of Influence of Artificial Intelligence technologies required in business education:	\bar{x}	Std. Dev	Decision
1	AI supports the presentation of a lecture on business education	3.35	0.82	HE
2	AI assists lecturers to carry out research in business education	3.16	0.84	HE
3	AI helps lecturers to provide community services	3.22	0.79	HE
4	AI assists lecturers to develop their course notes	3.28	0.89	HE
5	AI aids effective classroom management	3.14	0.74	HE
6	AI aids lecturers to assign assignment and projects to students	3.34	0.83	HE
7	AI aids in distance learning education	3.32	0.94	HE
8	AI supports individual learning and collaborative learning	3.15	0.85	HE
9	AI assists students in writing their research work in business education	3.16	0.90	HE
10	AI assists effective conduct of examinations in business education	3.23	0.92	HE
11	AI supports presentation of lectures in business education	3.24	0.91	HE
Aggregate Mean				
Criterion Mean				

Testing of the Hypotheses

The data presented in table 1 shows that the mean rating of the responses of the respondents on all the items are highly needed (Mean = 2.5 and above).

1. There is no significant difference in the mean rating between male and female on extent of Artificial Intelligence technologies required in business education in South-South Universities in Nigeria.

Table 3: Mean ratings between male and female on extent of Artificial Intelligence technologies required in business education in South-South Universities in Nigeria.

Variables	N	Mean	SD	t-cal.	df	t. value	Decision
Male	135	3.07	0.84	1.03	234	1.96	Accepted
Female	101	3.01	0.91				

Since the t-cal (1.03) is less than t. value 1.96 at significance level of 0.05, the null hypothesis is accepted.

2. There is no significant difference in the mean rating between male and female on extent of the influence of Artificial Intelligence technologies required in business education in South-South Universities in Nigeria.

Table 4: Mean ratings between male and female on extent of the influence of Artificial Intelligence technologies required in business education in South-South Universities in Nigeria

Variables	N	Mean	SD	t-cal.	df	t. value	Decision
Male	135	3.15	0.81	1.15	234	1.96	Accepted
Female	101	3.09	0.79				

Since the t-cal (1.15) is less than t. value 1.96 at significance level of 0.05, the null hypothesis is accepted.

3. There is no significant difference in the mean rating between state and federal university lecturers on extent of Artificial Intelligence technologies required in business education in South-South Universities in Nigeria.

Table 5: Mean ratings between state and federal university lecturers on extent of Artificial Intelligence technologies required in business education in South-South Universities in Nigeria

Variables	N	Mean	SD	t-cal.	df	t. value	Decision
State	141	3.16	0.86	1.06	234	1.96	Accepted
Federal	95	3.11	0.87				

Since the t-cal (1.06) is less than t. value 1.96 at significance level of 0.05, the null hypothesis is accepted.

4. There is no significant difference in the mean rating between state and federal university lecturers on extent of the influence of Artificial Intelligence technologies required in business education in South-South Universities in Nigeria

Table 6: Mean ratings between state and federal university lecturers on extent of the influence of Artificial Intelligence technologies required in business education in South-South Universities in Nigeria

Variables	N	Mean	SD	t-cal.	df	t. value	Decision
State	141	3.21	0.79	1.12	234	1.96	Accepted
Federal	95	3.13	0.81				

Since the t-cal (1.12) is less than t. value 1.96 at significance level of 0.05, the null hypothesis is accepted.

Discussion of Findings

The findings on research question one reveal that Artificial Intelligence technologies required in business education in South-South Universities in Nigeria are to a high extent. Some of these are: AI-powered educational games, Adaptive learning platforms, Intelligent Tutoring System (ITS), Expert System (ES), Machine-assisted classroom, Deep-Learning (DL), Voice assistant technologies, Robotics, Machine Vision (MV) and Automated Facial Recognition (FR). The findings are consistent with earlier studies of Eze, Igwe and Okah (2023) and Olom, Kulo & Atah (2025) who earlier identified Artificial Intelligence technologies required in business education.

The findings of the hypotheses on research question 1 are: There is no significant difference in the mean rating between male and female on extent of Artificial Intelligence technologies required in business education in South-South Universities in Nigeria and there is no significant difference in the mean rating between state and federal university lecturers on extent of Artificial Intelligence technologies required in business education in South-South Universities in Nigeria

The findings on research question two reveal that the extent of influence of Artificial Intelligence technologies required in business education in South-South Universities in Nigeria are to a high extent. Some of these are AI support the presentation of a lecture on business education, AI assists lecturers to carry out research in business education, AI helps the lecturer to provide community services, AI assists lecturers to develop their course note, AI aid effective classroom management, AI aid lecturers to assign assignment and projects to students, AI distance learning education, AI support individual learning and collaborate learning, AI assists students in writing their research work in business and AI assists effective examinations in business and AI support presentation of lecture on business education. The findings are consistent with earlier studies of Eze, Igwe and Okah (2023) and Olom, Kulo & Atah (2025) who earlier identified the influences of Artificial Intelligence technologies required in business education.

The findings of the hypotheses on research question 2 are: There is no significant difference in the mean rating between male and female on the extent of influence of Artificial Intelligence technologies required in business education in South-South Universities in Nigeria and there is no significant difference in the mean rating between state and federal university lecturers on the extent of influence of Artificial Intelligence technologies required in business education in South-South Universities in Nigeria.

Conclusion

Application of AI technologies in the teaching and learning of business education programme in universities by business education lecturers is very essential. The utilization of AI technologies offers benefits such as enhanced personalized learning, streamlined administrative tasks, improved research support. It also facilitates collaboration and the need to address ethical considerations. Since the area of artificial intelligence is changing, lecturers should adopt ICT modern tools to keep up to date on the latest advancements.

Recommendations

The following recommendations are made for the study:

1. School authorities should provide Intelligent Tutoring System (ITS) for lecturers and adaptive learning platforms for learners in business education departments.
2. School authorities should provide adequate environment for use of AI to assists lecturers to carry out research in business education.
3. School authorities should provide relevant activities for improving lecturers' adaptive learning methods required for the use of AI for business education research.

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